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Abstract

The global demand for scientists and engineers has increased the imperative for large transnational firms, cities, and nations to train, attract and retain highly skilled scientific personnel. Scientists move in and out of many laboratories, cities and countries through their training, careers and occupational activities. In doing so, they create research networks (dispersed knowledge networks). These networks endure long after they have moved on elsewhere. In this article we argue that it is not so much current location that is important for 'brain-drain' or 'brain-gain' but rather the places scientists have been and the networks and 'scientific conduits' they have laid down in their travels. There is potential for developing countries exporting skilled scientists to cities elsewhere to enhance science capability by 'plugging in' to these networks. We use empirical data from a survey of over 10,000 scientists and engineers from the Asia-Pacific to investigate and map this network building process.

KEYWORDS: dispersed knowledge networks; science networks; brain-drain; Asia Pacific migration; skilled migration; science careers

Introduction

The loss or gain of skills and expertise through the migration of highly skilled professionals has been a concern of states around the world for some time (Iredale 1997; Meyer 2001; Gaillard & Gaillard 1997). In the 1960s, the US drew attention to the potential national benefit of the post-war influx of scientists (US House of Representatives 1977). The human capital model of scientific productivity emerged around this time, arguing that scientific output peaked and then declined in relation to the individual life cycle (Stephan & Levin 2002). Derived from economics, this model focused on the individual, with the mobility of scientists becoming viewed as a zero-sum game benefiting receiving countries to the detriment of sending countries. Due to the high level of investment of time and money required to train a scientist in comparison to the cost of exploiting natural resources, it came to be believed that the gap between developed and developing countries would continue to widen (Lyotard 1984, p. 5). A net outward migration of talented students and scientists was thus held to have considerable negative long-term consequences for a country.

Since the mid-1970s the world of scientific training and careers has changed dramatically. In 1989, for example, the opening of the Iron Curtain resulted in a huge increase in the outflow of scientific personnel from the former Soviet countries, notably to Israel. A number of studies since the 1980s have shown how the immigration of scientists and engineers from developing countries to the US, Israel, Canada and Great Britain contributed to the growth of scientific and innovative capacity in the North (Arocena & Sutz 2006). These science intensive population movements provided a major contribution to knowledge intensive growth centres in the US, the UK, Canada, Germany and Australia (TIAC 2002).

Since the mid-1990s, the sustained growth of the large economies of China and India has led to an increasing demand for the world's scientists. There is now evidence that knowledge intensity in East and Southern Asia over the next decade will continue to expand, with the world's large business R&D spenders locating 75 per cent of their new R&D investments in India and China (Doz et al. 2006). Singapore, already emerging as a new regional knowledge hub for medical research, is attracting some of the world's top medical researchers. For example, Dr Alan Coleman, the specialist behind the cloning of 'Dolly the sheep' in the UK, was recruited as principal investigator at the Institute of Medical Biology (IMB) and as Executive Director of the Singapore Stem Cell Consortium. It was not just Dr Coleman's expertise that attracted his recruiters, but a recognition that his appointment would serve to attract more of the world's best researchers to the region. As the IMB's director put it: 'A world renowned scientist like Dr Coleman*who created Dolly, the world's first cloned sheep*will help draw good people to Singapore' (Kesava 2007a, 2007b).

There are two marked trends in the race to attract, train, and retain scientific and technological personnel as innovation experts who make a valuable contribution to a nation's innovation and production systems. The first is that some countries are losing science and technology-trained personnel and are much concerned about the erosion of their hard-won scientific capability through an international brain-drain. The second is the creation of transnational innovation networks made up of local and expatriate scientists and known as Distributed Knowledge Networks (OECD 2002) or, as others have defined them in the migration literature, as Diaspora Knowledge Networks (DKNs in both cases). In

this article, we argue that this second trend has the potential to mitigate the effects of the first trend, particularly by enabling developing countries to leverage the involvement of their nationals in networks. We use empirical data, from a survey of scientists and engineers from the Asia-Pacific region, to highlight the way researchers from the region have been involved in global circulation and network building.

This article argues that the focus on the migration or mobility of personnel and their embodied knowledge and skills tends to miss an important point: that scientists are essentially network builders. Throughout their training, career development, and occupational activities, they may move in and out of many countries' research laboratories, universities and collaborative projects. In doing so, they create research linkages and conduits for knowledge flows that endure long after they have moved on elsewhere. Thus, it is not so much current location that is important for brain-drain or brain-gain but rather the places scientists have been and the networks and 'scientific conduits' they have laid down in their travels. This opens the potential for DKNs to become a significant part of dispersed knowledge networks and thus provide a valuable flow of knowledge to their home countries and emerging regional knowledge hubs.

Our analysis reveals how location and experiences of research training and postdoctoral work are formative in the development of international networks. While patterns of mobility vary according to country of origin and fields of scientific study, the underlying feature of network building is the same. Research training and post-doctoral locations and experiences are key drivers for future career networking and collaboration. The implications for emerging scientific knowledge hubs such as China, India and Singapore are not simply how to retain or gain scientific personnel, but how to build and gain access to their networks as mobile scientists move in and out of countries throughout their careers.

From Managing the Brain Drain to Leveraging Networks

The generation and circulation of scientific knowledge is intricately interwoven with patterns of mobility of scientists, engineers and other technical specialists. According to Mahroum (1999, p. 189), 'nations increasingly view technology transfer as primarily a people-oriented phenomenon', with the human capital flows through education and migration central to national innovation policies (David & Foray 2002; Laudel 2005; OECD 1997, 2002; Powell & Snellman 2004; Tzeng 2006). International, national and regional policy-makers have moved from trying to manage the 'brain gain/ drain/train' to seeking appropriate ways to 'frame' the global market (Callon 2002) for scientific skills in the interests of economic growth, social development and fairness (Dickson 2003; Drori et al. 2003; Interacademy Council 2004; OECD 2002; Skeldon 2007; UNCTAD 2005).

An emerging way of conceptualising the interrelated questions of flows of scientific knowledge and science personnel is through the DKNs. These new networks, centred in developed countries but linking developing ones, have the potential to contribute to solving some of the many issues confronting both poorer and richer countries (Leclerc & Meyer 2007; Meyer & Wattiaux 2006; Mahroum & De Guchteneire 2006). The definition and empirical analysis of DKNs has, to a large extent, 'subverted the traditional "brain drain" migration outflow into a "brain gain" skills circulation by converting the loss of human resources into a remote although accessible asset of expanded networks' (Meyer & Wattiaux 2006, p. 5).

Empirical studies of these DKNs' functionings have so far focused primarily on networks in the Americas (Meyer et al. 1999) and Africa (Meyer et al. 2001). Diasporas of scientific personnel may create positive externalities that boost the innovative capacity of developing countries by providing readily accessible new knowledge, ideas and skills (Leclerc & Meyer 2007). Knowledge networks can contribute to innovation and international learning by producing new knowledge through transdisciplinary research on problems as they are experienced across international boundaries and operational knowledge is acquired through context-bound interactions across various sectors (Stein et al. 2001, p. 4). Stein et al.'s case study analyses thus emphasise the dissemination of knowledge through networks and contributions that carry global knowledge into local contexts. This 'new localism' in science represents something of a global transformation in the social relations of the production of knowledge through the extension and overlapping of scientific networks.

DKNs are also a feature of scientific knowledge production in the Asia-Pacific region. For example, Biao (2007) has shown how national diaspora networks in the information technology (IT) sectors of India and China have different outcomes in terms of local outputs (socio-economic development and basic research, respectively) depending on whether they are predominantly framed by multinational market actors (India) or institutional policies (China). Ramirez and Dickenson (2007) have shown how China, through the Zhongguancun Science Park in Beijing, has integrated its R&D activity into global scientific and industrial networks. Their study reveals the importance of DKNs, with one entrepreneur commenting on the 'importance of the "Tsinghua entrepreneurial group" formed in Silicon Valley around the millennium, most of whose members have now returned to Beijing' (Ramirez & Dickenson 2006, p. 35).

While China and India are now attracting global flows of R&D funding and scientific personnel (Dente 2007), disparate levels of scientific capability and rates of capacity building remain throughout the Asia-Pacific (Drori et al. 2003; Interacademy Council 2004; UNCTAD 2005). However, what appears to be emerging, for both developed and developing countries alike, is a re-framing of the question of scientific mobility away from how to manage the 'brain drain' and towards how best to integrate into, and subsequently leverage, the knowledge and capability flowing through DKNs.

Building Knowledge Conduits through Research Training

The training of a research scientist is a fundamental building block for both an individual career and the networks of collaboration and exchange in which the scientist becomes involved. Travelling overseas to undertake a PhD or post-doctoral position constitutes a mobility mechanism (Coe & Bunnell 2003) for professional scientists, a movement that proceeds '... through channels of institutions that enjoy a high reputation for excellence and expertise' (Mahroum 2000, p. 367). The research training or postdoctoral phase takes place largely through universities, research centres or government laboratories, constituting a public sector institutional framing of these movements. In many cases these institutions lay down patterns for mobility as senior scientific staff mentor younger colleagues to train at the same institutions they attended. However, as we argue later, the growth of new regional knowledge hubs has the capacity to steer new students in new directions.

Research training inculcates forms of tacit knowledge, sets of technical competences and regimes of theoretical knowledge that underpin disciplines and research fields. International movements by young scientists for research training thus determine to some degree the distribution of knowledge and the transfer of technologies. Where scientists go to train undoubtedly matters. Research scientists frequently seek to enter the labour market through post-doctoral research positions. This is the career juncture where the scientific capitals acquired through research training can be developed and deployed in the emergence of a relatively autonomous research trajectory. International studies highlight post-doctoral research positions as a key strategy for recently trained scientists in both these regards (Lancio-Morandat & Nohara 2002; Marceau & Preston 1997). Postdoctoral positions are highly sought after and selective (Lancio-Morandat & Nohara 2002; Marceau & Preston 1997), particularly those in prestigious research institutes, laboratories or universities. Post-doctoral appointments accrue significant scientific credit to their holders, whilst integrating them into networks with access to the best facilities and resources, research teams. The knowledge conduits built in and out of the Asia-Pacific region by personnel moving to undertake PhD training or taking up post-doctoral positions can thus be expected to structure significantly the broader patterns of DKNs in the region.

The mobility and networks of internationally trained scientists are also important from a development perspective. That the North American and European science systems are the most attractive destinations for talented researchers from developing economies is well-known (OECD 2002). Many nations have policies designed to attract the return of their nationals (Fontes 2007; Laudel 2005; Tzeng 2006; Zweig 1997). As important as the 'return' of skilled scientists and technologists is to national innovation systems, DKNs based around national or cultural diasporas are also emerging as important contributors to capacity-building in developing countries (Leclerc & Meyer 2007), building knowledge conduits via 'personalised networks' (Wellman 2001) that facilitate the transfer of knowledge and technology at a distance.

Methodology

The survey methodology that underpins this article was exploratory and based on a convenience sample drawn from the Science Citation Index (SCI) database (which excludes the social sciences and humanities). Author, institutional and email addresses of all papers for 2004 with at least one author from 22 Asia-Pacific locations were downloaded. This information was collated according to the country of lead author. The number of addresses collected for each of the 22 locations was approximately proportionate to the numbers of papers from these locations published in SCI journals in 2004.

An email inviting authors to participate in the survey was sent out which contained a link to a project and survey information page, along with an individual identification number and password to access the survey. The information page was available in English, Chinese, Japanese and Korean; the survey, however, was only available in English. The number of emails actual delivered was estimated at 50,000. A large number of emails bounced when sent (n=20,000). The total number of useable responses received was 10,132. Approximately four-fifths of respondents were from the researcher defined Asia-Pacific region. The leading co-author nationalities outside the region were the US and the UK. Respondents were predominantly male (85.5 per cent), with varying participation of

female respondents observable for the different nationalities. Particularly strong female participation among respondents was evident from Thailand and the Philippines.

Table 1 shows the number of responses by gender for the 22 locations that defined the region on which the study sample was based. Table 1 also shows the number and gender of co-author respondents who were from outside the defined region. These 'other' nationalities also provide a guide to patterns of international research collaboration.

TABLE 1
Respondents' nationality and gender.

Nationality	Male	Female	Total	% Total
<i>Asia-Pacific locations</i>				
Australia	795	239	1034	10.21
Bangladesh	68	3	71	0.70
PR China	1449	193	1642	16.21
Hong Kong	44	6	50	0.49
India	1435	226	1661	16.39
Indonesia	30	9	39	0.38
Japan	1241	69	1310	12.93
Korea	689	47	736	7.26
Malaysia	110	46	156	1.54
New Zealand	240	74	314	3.10
Pakistan	82	16	98	0.97
Papua New Guinea	4	0	4	0.04
Philippines	29	26	55	0.54
Singapore	96	19	115	1.14
Sri Lanka	33	10	43	0.42
Taiwan	371	58	429	4.23
Thailand	121	96	217	2.14
Tonga	0	1	1	0.01
Vietnam	27	6	33	0.33
Total Asia-Pacific	6864	1144	8008	79.04
<i>Major co-author locations</i>				
Austria	19	5	24	0.24
Belgium	31	3	34	0.34
Brazil	21	1	22	0.22
Canada	105	20	125	1.23
Denmark	22	2	24	0.24
France	104	21	125	1.23
Germany	179	16	195	1.92
Iran	22	1	23	0.23
Italy	61	10	71	0.70
Korea (PR)	28	7	35	0.35
Netherlands	54	9	63	0.62
Poland	18	5	23	0.23
Russian Federation	70	2	72	0.71
Spain	26	10	36	0.36
Sweden	31	6	37	0.37
UK	202	44	246	2.43
US	442	81	523	5.16
Total co-author locations	1435	243	1678	16.56
Others	362	84	446	4.40
Total	8661	1471	10132	100.00

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Figure 1 shows the age distribution of respondents for three nationalities and for the respondent group as a whole. Responses from China were somewhat biased toward younger scientists aged 45 or less in comparison to the other nationalities shown and the respondent group overall. This may be related to language proficiency, the rapidly expanding scale of the Chinese science effort and the relatively recent increasing level of geo-political integration of Chinese institutions globally. Indian nationals were a comparatively older age group.

FIGURE 1
Age curve: selected sample countries. *Source:* Scientists Survey 2006.

Other biases in the respondent population might be toward those that have trained in English language countries and perhaps those whose employment tenure is less secure, as their career pathway will be of more pressing concern. As the methodology was exploratory, the results should therefore be viewed as indicative rather than representative of the wider scientific community in the region.

Network Building Activity of Researchers from Selected North Asian Countries, India and Australia

This section provides an overview of the patterns of international mobility for research training and for take up of post-doctoral positions among scientists from the selected North Asian countries of Japan, the People's Republic of China (PR China), India, Korea and Taiwan. Australia is included as a comparator because of historical scientific and linguistic links with the US and UK. Data from three South Asian (Bangladesh, Pakistan and Sri Lanka) and six South-east Asian countries (Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand and Vietnam) are contrasted in the following section. These three groups enable some comparisons to be made and to show how researchers from smaller science systems may be linked into the regions established and emerging networks in science and innovation through research training.

Overall, 1225 (18.3 per cent) respondents from the six selected locations shown in Table 2 did their research degree overseas, or 20.3 per cent of those with a research degree qualification. Diversity is evident amongst the six locations, both in the rates of international research degrees and in the variety of international destinations where this research training was done. Respondents from Taiwan and Korea were relatively more likely to be trained overseas. Japanese respondents overwhelmingly did their PhDs at home. Respondents from Japan, Korea and Taiwan were more narrowly selective about international training destinations. Respondents from the PR China, India, and Australia were less selective in training destinations, although this data most likely reflects the size and spread of the Chinese and Indian diasporas and the high level of skilled migration to Australia. A significant variation is also evident in the return rate of those who trained overseas.¹ Around half of those respondents from the PR China who trained overseas had remained abroad, whereas only around one in ten of those from Japan, Korea and Taiwan were not currently working in their home location.

TABLE 2

International research training: selected North Asian countries, India and Australia.

Economy	Respondents (n)	Respondents with research degree (n)	International research degrees		
			Rate (%)	No. of destinations	Return rate (%)
Australia	1010	920	24.2	27	81.0
PR China	1620	1447	20.9	32	50.2
India	1637	1478	14.1	28	74.5
Japan	1290	1171	4.0	10	91.5
Korea	727	663	38.9	13	90.7
Taiwan	424	349	56.2	15	90.4
Total	6708	6037	18.3	n/a	85.2

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Table 3 summarises selected data regarding post-doctoral positions for respondents from these six locations. A total of 1954 respondents (29.1 per cent) from the six locations being analysed took up post-doctoral research positions in an overseas location. This was a higher rate in comparison to research training (18.3 per cent). The most noticeable difference between data presented for research training and for post-doctoral positions is that related to Japan. The rate of participation of Japanese in international research training compared to the post-doctoral level is low. These data reflect the particularity of the Japanese higher education and research systems (Whitley 2000). In comparison, the proportion of overseas post-doctorates and the number of destinations for these positions for respondents from the other locations were far greater. Overall, it is clear that these scientists from the Asia-Pacific region have been highly mobile, moving in and out of cities through this phase of their research careers. Table 4 summarises the major destinations where respondents did their research training and Table 5 summarises where respondents took up post-doctoral positions.

TABLE 3

Post-doctoral research positions: selected North Asian countries, India and Australia.

Economy	Respondents (n)	Respondents held post- doctorates (%)	International post-doctorates		
			Rate (%)	No. of destinations	Return rate (%)
Australia	1010	46.0	26.8	27	75.1
PR China	1620	39.7	24.5	39	62.3
India	1637	46.3	31.7	38	80.7
Japan	1290	44.2	31.0	26	92.2
Korea	727	51.0	40.2	16	90.1
Taiwan	424	30.3	17.7	8	91.8
Total	6708	43.8	29.1	n/a	80.4

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

International research training (Table 4) undertaken by respondents was concentrated in a small number of locations. The US was the favoured destination for all respondent groups

except Australia and PR China. In the Australia case, this can be explained by historical links with the UK. Other significant locations of PhD training for Australian respondents were New Zealand (8.0 per cent) and Russia (5.6 per cent).

TABLE 4

Major international destinations for PhD research training: selected North Asian countries, India and Australia (percentage of overseas destinations).

Destination	Australia	PR China	India	Japan	Korea	Taiwan
Canada	5.6	0.0	4.8	0.0	2.3	2.0
Germany	0.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	3.1	2.0
Japan	0.0	17.9	2.9	0.0	12.8	4.1
Singapore	0.0	13.2	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0
UK	43.7	7.3	14.8	17.0	3.1	7.7
US	17.8	16.9	47.4	55.3	70.9	76.0

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Note: Cell values less than two per cent and with insignificant cell numbers are shown, as 0.0.

Respondents from the PR China were equally likely to stay within the Asia-Pacific region than to move further afield for research training, with Japan and Singapore the major suppliers of training to PR China respondents. Other destinations for research training amongst Chinese respondents included Hong Kong (8.9 per cent), France (4.0 per cent), Australia (2.6 per cent) and Sweden (2.6 per cent). Respondents from Korea and Taiwan favoured US training destinations overwhelmingly, whilst Indian respondents were also most likely to go to the US but with another large group heading to the UK.

The US was the major destination for post-doctoral positions for respondents from all six locations. The US emphasis was particularly strong for those from Taiwan, Korea and Japan. After the UK, Germany was the most prominent amongst European destination for emerging researchers, including a particularly prominent relationship with Indian respondents. Unsurprisingly, given its advanced science and research system, Japan was the most important Asian destination for post-doctoral positions. The most diverse group in terms of destinations were those from China, who also reported the lowest level of participation in the US system at the post-doctoral level. Canada and the UK were also prominent destinations for taking up post-doctoral positions, but diversity in the mix of destinations for post-doctorates was clearly evident in comparing these six groups.

TABLE 5

Major international destinations for post-doctoral positions: selected North Asian countries, India and Australia (percentage of overseas destinations).

Destination	Australia	PR China	India	Japan	Korea	Taiwan
Canada	12.2	0.0	6.2	7.3	4.5	0.0
France	0.0	7.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Germany	4.4	8.1	11.8	5.8	4.5	0.0
Japan	0.0	16.9	5.8	0.0	7.9	0.0
Singapore	0.0	7.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
UK	21.4	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	5.7
US	40.6	25.2	43.5	68.3	73.6	80.0

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Note: Cell values less than two per cent and with insignificant cell numbers are shown as 0.0.

However, as Tables 4 and 5 show, overall the US was the leading destination for both PhD training and post-doctoral positions among respondents. To assess linkages between international mobility for research training and postdoctoral positions and network building, we asked respondents the main sites of their research networks. We also asked respondents about the location of researchers with whom their most important transnational knowledge producing collaboration had taken place, with knowledge production defined according to standard measures of output (e.g. journal publication, patent, etc.). Major results from these two questions are shown in Table 6.

At an aggregate level, all six selected economic groups, except the PR China, nominated the US as the number one location of their research networks. In all cases, networks were dominated by a combination of 'home' location and the US. Japan was significant in relation to networks with respondents from East Asia. Australian respondents' networks are mainly contained within the Anglophone world. Table 5 also highlights the central position of US based researchers in transnational collaborations.

The significance of Japan and Germany as partners in research collaboration is also evident, whilst the UK retains its position as most important for respondents from other Commonwealth countries (Australia and India). Comparison of the results shown in Table 6 with those in Tables 4 and 5 show very consistent patterns of research training and post-doctoral locations and networks building. The US is the number one location for research training, post-doctoral research positions for emergent researchers, and for networking relationships and collaborations. Other strong suppliers of training and early career positions to the respondents, particularly Japan, Germany and the UK, are also the major sites of networks and collaborators for particular respondent groups. Based on this descriptive evidence we can confidently argue that the paths in and out of Asia-Pacific taken by science researchers from the region, whether for research training or to take up early career post-doctoral appointments, are closely related to the networks and therefore, the knowledge conduits they build.

TABLE 6

International networks and transnational research collaborations: selected North Asian countries, India and Australia (by percentage).

Location	Australia	PR China	India	Japan	Korea	Taiwan
<i>Networks</i>						
Australia	29.1					
PR China		27.9				
India			24.5			
Japan		11.5		23.3	14.4	
Korea					18.5	
Taiwan						21.9
Germany			11.0	5.1		
UK	12.3					6.8
US	34.0	26.0	29.8	50.4	49.3	56.2
<i>Collaborations</i>						
Australia	8.9					
PR China		9.1		5.2		
India			8.7			
Japan		15.7			17.1	10.3
Canada						4.5
Germany		7.1	16.2	6.5	4.5	4.5
UK	14.0		7.7	5.5		5.9
US	36.4	29.4	30.8	53.5	53.8	57.4

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Note: Data are shown only for values above four per cent.

Network Building Activity of Researchers from South and South-east Asian Countries

This section summarises data on international mobility for research training and network building for respondents from the three South Asian countries of Bangladesh, Pakistan and Sri Lanka, and the six South-east Asian countries of Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Philippines, Thailand and Vietnam. The locations of research networks and research collaborators are analysed for the three countries with larger numbers of respondents Malaysia, Singapore and Thailand. Data on international mobility for postdoctoral research positions is not analysed for any of these countries due to the small numbers involved.

The proportions of international training undertaken by respondents from South and South-east Asia are much higher than those observed amongst respondents from the larger knowledge producing countries (apart from Taiwan). These data support the argument that scientific research training capacity has not yet been built to the same extent in many of these countries compared to the larger knowledge producing centres of the Asian region. The range of international training rates across these nine countries varied from approximately half (Pakistan 52.1 per cent) to almost nine out of every ten amongst Indonesian respondents (89.5 per cent). The spread of training destinations appears relatively consistent across the nine countries as shown in Table 7, with only Singapore showing a narrower range of choices relative to the number of respondents involved in international research training.

The overall return rate of those who did their research training overseas (72.3 percent) is lower than that for the respondents from the North Asia and Australian group of countries (80.4 per cent). However, this overall rate is boosted by the very high rates of return of respondents to Thailand and Singapore, two locations with relatively high numbers of

overseas trained respondents. The other country with a relatively large number of overseas-trained respondents, Malaysia, has a much lower return rate in comparison. The other return rates should be viewed cautiously due to the quite small numbers of cases involved.

TABLE 7
International research training: selected South and South-east Asian countries.

Economy	Respondents (n)	Respondents with research degree (n)	International research degrees		
			Rate (%)	No. of destinations	Return rate (%)
<i>South Asia</i>					
Bangladesh	71	62	72.6	14	62.8
Pakistan	98	71	52.1	12	61.3
Sri Lanka	43	39	74.4	12	59.3
<i>South-east Asia</i>					
Indonesia	39	38	89.5	12	63.3
Malaysia	157	140	72.9	13	56.3
Philippines	55	49	57.1	7	80.0
Singapore	112	97	59.8	8	88.7
Thailand	217	189	65.1	18	93.2
Vietnam	33	30	65.7	13	35.0
Total	825	715	68.6	n/a	72.3

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Table 8 summarises the international destinations for research training of respondents from South and South-east Asia. The UK was the leading supplier of training to respondents from four of the countries (Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Malaysia and Singapore); Japan was the leading supplier of training to respondents from three countries (Bangladesh, Indonesia, Philippines); whilst the US was the major supplier of training for Singapore, Philippines and Thailand. Also noticeable was the more prominent role of Australia for those from Indonesia and Singapore, whilst Singapore and Germany were also prominent destinations for those from Indonesia and Malaysia and from Vietnam respectively. Notably, for the Asia-Pacific region, Malaysia and Singapore are also centres for training for a number of other Asian countries (Vietnam, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka and Indonesia).

The breakdown of research training destinations was thus quite different in comparison with the North Asia and Australian group described earlier. The US was less prominent among respondents from the South and South-east Asian countries than among respondents from the larger knowledge producing locations. Respondents from Bangladesh and Indonesia had built most of their research training links within the Asia-Pacific region, although North America and Europe still provided 62.0 per cent of all the international research degrees to respondents from these nine locations overall. In fact, as might be expected, training destinations for respondents from the South and Southeast Asian countries also appear to bear traces of historical geo-political relationships, particularly in relation to the sizeable number of countries in this group with ties to Britain, such as Pakistan, Malaysia and Singapore, and to the US, such as Singapore, Philippines and Thailand. Singapore was also a focus for research training for China.

TABLE 8

Major international destinations for PhD research training: selected South and South-east Asian countries (percentage of overseas destinations).

Destination	Bangladesh	Pakistan	Sri Lanka	Indonesia	Malaysia	Philippines	Singapore	Thailand	Vietnam
Australia	4.5	0.0	6.9	20.6	8.8	14.3	14.0	10.4	5.0
Canada	0.0	5.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.7	10.3	0.0	0.0
Germany	0.0	5.4	0.0	5.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	10.0
Japan	37.8	5.4	6.9	26.5	5.9	25.0	0.0	12.0	20.0
Malaysia	6.7	0.0	0.0	5.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	20.0
Singapore	0.0	0.0	6.9	11.8	9.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0
UK	20.0	37.8	41.4	0.0	52.0	0.0	36.2	18.4	0.0
US	6.7	21.6	13.8	5.9	11.8	39.3	27.6	39.2	0.0

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Note: Cell values less than two per cent and with insignificant cell numbers are shown as 0.0.

Table 9 shows the networks and collaboration for three of the South-east Asian countries, Malaysia, Singapore and Thailand. These were chosen because there were more respondents from these countries. Comparing Table 9 with Table 8, it can be seen that the nominated locations of networks and collaborations correspond quite closely to the international research training destinations for respondents from each of these three groups. However, the patterns are distinct in each of the three cases. The emphasis amongst Malaysian respondents is on mobility to the UK and the US, with networks and collaborations also most prevalent with colleagues in these two countries. The next strongest level of relationships for Malaysian respondents involves mobility to, and networks with, Japan, Singapore and Australia. In networks and collaborative research. Rather, networks are built most strongly with the US, though the UK, Australia, China, Canada and Germany are important partners. However, Japan does not feature as a training destination amongst Singaporean respondents and remains very weakly linked in terms of network building. Singaporean respondents were much more likely to nominate researchers based in their own country as the main location of their networks, than were Malaysian or Thai respondents. This seems to reflect Singapore's growing scientific strength and its role in the development of an emerging regional knowledge hub. In the case of Thailand, respondents' major training destinations*US, UK, Japan and Australia*are also the strongly predominant locations of networks and for partners in collaboration.

A comparison of data for the two groups of countries leaves three fairly distinct impressions. First, there are lower rates of international training in the North Asian group. Secondly, international training and networking is more heavily concentrated in the US amongst respondents from the North Asian countries. Thirdly, researchers from the South and South-east Asian countries are also linking into the more developed Asian economies through research training-enabled network building activity. These networks and collaborations appear to be more evenly distributed between North America, Europe and the Asia-Pacific region than for the North Asian group of countries.

TABLE 9

Research networks and transnational research collaborations: Malaysia, Singapore and Thailand (by percentage).

Location	Malaysia	Singapore	Thailand
<i>Networks</i>			
Malaysia	12.8	0.0	0.0
Singapore	4.7	27.9	0.0
Thailand	0.0	0.0	11.9
Australia	5.4	4.5	9.9
Canada	3.4	2.7	2.0
PR China	0.0	4.5	1.0
Germany	1.4	2.7	3.0
Japan	12.8	0.0	18.8
UK	21.6	9.9	9.9
US	18.9	45.0	25.2
<i>Collaborations</i>			
Malaysia	6.9	0.0	0.0
Singapore	6.9	14.8	0.0
Thailand	0.0	1.0	7.0
Australia	4.2	6.5	8.5
Canada	3.5	2.8	2.0
PR China	1.4	8.3	1.0
Germany	0.0	3.7	2.0
Japan	13.9	3.7	19.9
UK	24.3	10.2	13.9
US	19.4	39.8	25.9

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Note: Cell values less than one per cent and with insignificant cell numbers are shown as 0.0.

The Ins and Outs of Global Scientific Development

The previous sections describe the role of research training and post-doctoral experiences in building research networks. This discussion focuses primarily on the implications for scientists and the countries through which their training and career trajectories take them. Our general argument is that these networks, once formed and deepened through further research collaboration, remain as 'science conduits' through which knowledge and ideas flow irrespective of the country in which these scientists might subsequently be employed. This raises the possibility that through progressive locations and time spent with collaborating partners, scientific disciplines may undergo change. As networks deepen, through geographic location as well as virtual location, the ways scientific questions are framed and the quest for possible solutions are funded and approached carries the potential to reframe the scientific mission in certain fields (Hill 1995).

We have attempted to further map some of these science networks and conduits by testing for statistical relationships between international mobility for training or postdoctorates and the building of research networks and transnational collaborations, comparing between seven broad scientific disciplines. Each of the respondents from the six large knowledge producing locations in Asia-Pacific was allocated to one of the seven disciplinary groups on the basis of the field of their doctoral research. All scientific fields showed correlations² between the destination for research degree and location of main international networks. With the exception of engineering, the correlation was higher for destination for post-doctorates and location of research networks. For all fields of research, the relationship between location of post-doctorates and country of most

important collaboration was considerably stronger than the correlation between location of research degree and most important collaboration (Table 10).

The correlation tests suggest that both PhD training and post-doctoral positions contribute to the formation of networks and collaborations. Destinations for PhDs and post-doctorates appear to have relatively equivalent influence on the shape of research networks. The strengths of the correlations are relatively similar, suggesting the impacts of PhD training and post-doctoral positions on network formation are of a similar magnitude. These results appear consistent across all the research fields analysed. However, postdoctoral positions appear to have a relatively stronger influence on collaborative knowledge production relationships. The tests indicate that this is the case across all seven broad disciplines. On the basis of these data, it thus appears that whilst international mobility for post-doctoral research positions is relatively strongly tied to subsequent transnational knowledge production arrangements amongst researchers from Asia-Pacific, this effect is felt relatively evenly across scientific disciplines.

TABLE 10

Correlations between research training and post-doctorates and international networks and collaboration.

Field of research and country of research degree and post-doctorate	Research networks	Most important collaboration
1. Agricultural Science (research degree)	0.276**	0.105
2. Agricultural Science (post-doctorate)	0.370**	0.272**
1. Medical Health (research degree)	0.159**	0.040
2. Medical Health (post-doctorate)	0.298**	0.254**
1. Life Science (research degree)	0.172**	0.059*
2. Life Science (post-doctorate)	0.249**	0.276**
1. Chemical Sciences (research degree)	0.206**	0.031
2. Chemical Sciences (post-doctorate)	0.270**	0.242**
1. Engineering (research degree)	0.294**	0.176**
2. Engineering (post-doctorate)	0.292**	0.313**
1. Earth & Environmental Science (research degree)	0.234**	0.059
2. Earth & Environmental Science (post-doctorate)	0.241**	0.184**
1. Maths & Comm. (research degree)	0.308**	0.180**
2 Maths & Comm. (post-doctorate)	0.347**	0.290**
1. Physical Science (research degree)	0.224**	0.072**
2 Physical Science (post-doctorate)	0.284**	0.229**

Source: Scientists Survey 2006.

Note: 1 = location of research degree; 2 = location of post-doctorate.

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (one-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (one-tailed).

Conclusion

Scientists from the Asia-Pacific region have been participating in science globally over the past several decades. International mobility has been facilitated through PhD research training and early career post-doctoral research positions, funded largely through public sector institutions. Patterns of training have institutional characteristics that are a product of funding opportunity and scientific mentoring, but as regional scientific strength deepens it is likely the region will offer competing attractors. The participation of researchers from different locations within the region has occurred at different rates, with

differing focuses on particular offshore destinations and with varying degrees of diversity in offshore choices.

It is clear, however, that researchers from the five North Asian locations that were considered in this article have participated in science most strongly in North America, particularly in the US, and in Europe, particularly the UK and Germany. Japan has also been an important destination for training and particularly for post-doctoral work, whilst the emergence of Singapore as a desirable scientific destination is also apparent. What is also clear is that there are very strong return rates amongst those researchers who undertake training or post-doctoral work internationally. This was less the case in relation to respondents from the PR China, although this may be due also to complicating factors including the size of the Chinese diaspora and the relatively recent emergence of domestic Chinese science as a participant in more fully 'global' scientific agendas. Overall, it appears that scientists from the larger knowledge producing centres in the Asia-Pacific region are making choices to return and to transfer knowledge and technology.

The mobility of scientists to international destinations for research training and/or post-doctoral positions appears to be an important element in the building of DKNs. However, according to our statistical analysis, the take up of post-doctoral positions appeared to be most important, suggesting that this initial phase of a research career may be the most vital in the formation of durable networks. In particular, post-doctoral positions appeared strongly correlated to the organisation of transnational collaboration knowledge production activities.

The picture in relation to the South and South-east Asian countries featured is somewhat less clear, in part due to smaller numbers of survey respondents from them. However, it does appear that respondents from these countries have somewhat different patterns of mobility for research training than those from the North Asian countries. There appears to be more diversity in terms of destinations and a propensity for research training to link researchers into the established knowledge producing centres within the Asia-Pacific region to a relatively greater extent, with significant mobility to North America and Europe also evident. Interestingly, return rates among the internationally trained originating from South and South-east Asian countries do appear somewhat lower than those from the northern locations. Thailand and Singapore present exceptions, and this perhaps indicates their involvement in the development of a regional knowledge hub.

However, more robust data is required to confirm this impression. Research training and early career mobility are important factors in the structuring of DKNs, which has implications for the development of science and innovation systems in the region. Capacity building can be continuous through the leveraging of DKNs, particularly where transnational knowledge production occurs. Researchers from the region are clearly linking into networks and undertaking collaborations that build knowledge conduits that are global in scope. It appears that this is relatively consistent across scientific disciplines. In other words, many scientists and technologists from the region are choosing to return to Asia, but not necessarily at the expense of their global science ambitions.

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NOTES

1. Location of respondents' current job was used as a proxy for return rate.
2. These are based on Pearson's correlation coefficient test.

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